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SERVING THE UNDERSERVED: WHAT CAN DESIGNERS LEARN FROM RURAL APPRAISAL TECHNIQUES?

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ABSTRACT

In Base of the Pyramid projects products and services are designed for the poorest users. Designers in these projects often have a Western background and the users live in rural areas in non-Western cultures. This poses a challenge of cultural understanding for which several disciplines have developed techniques. This paper presents a comparison of rural appraisal techniques with contextmapping techniques, which results in five guidelines for designers related to (1) the empowerment of people, (2) materials and locations, (3) time, (4) biases and (5) attitude of the outsiders. The developers of rural appraisal techniques emphasize the importance of a bottom up approach in which local people have a leading role in their development. Design approaches are moving in this direction.

Keywords: contextual research, design method, base of the pyramid.

INTRODUCTION

Designers use a variety of methods, tools and techniques for the design of products that function well and fit the needs of those who use them. To inform themselves about the context of use, they use, for example, interviews and observations. They need those insights about intended users and their context to ensure that they design products the end users will desire and use and experience as intended. Contextmapping techniques (CMTs) (Sleeswijk Visser, 2005) have been developed to involve end users in expressing their needs and dreams in ways that can be used in the early phase of a design process. The insights gained from those expressions help designers

to generate ideas and concepts. Besides information and inspiration, the involvement of end users, and sometimes their participation in co-creating solutions, also helps to create a social basis for acceptance of the product to be designed.

A limitation of current CMTs is that they have been developed and applied mostly in Western cultures and make use of social interactions that may need substantial adaptations to work in other cultures (van Rijn et al., 2006; Siemerink et al., 2010). Furthermore, most work on user experience, including work with CMTs, has focused on individual needs and dreams; less has been done on understanding social-cultural processes between people (Postma, 2006). These two limitations appear when designers try to apply CMTs in cultures that they are not familiar with, such as in ‘Base of the Pyramid’ (BoP) projects. The term Base (or bottom) of the Pyramid project, first introduced by Prahalad (2005), refers to the majority of the world’s population that earns less than 2 USA\$ purchasing power parity per day. BoP projects aim to develop products and product service systems that contribute to the lives of the poorest people in the world.

An example (visualized in figure 1) is a mobile learning environment for rural villages in Kenya. Kikoa, a Dutch student design team, has developed a product service system for the Dutch foundation ‘Better Future’. The aim of the foundation is to support adults living in rural areas to develop social entrepreneurial skills by offering them education in their local situation and by connecting them to Kenyan entrepreneurs from urban places.

Figure 1. An example of a BoP project: the Mobile Academy (Kikoa, 2010)

Kikoa designed a mobile learning centre. It includes both a set of physical products as well as the procedure how this set of products can be put into action in an economically feasible and sustainable manner. To do so, Kikoa first needed to understand the user context, covering many aspects, such as user preferences and motivations relating to gender roles, learning styles and working routines. Therefore, a contextual user research has been conducted. However, it was not clear in advance if the contextmapping techniques would work well.

Designers are not the first that go ‘out there’ to improve life conditions in the BoP and they may benefit from the experiences and insights gained in other disciplines. Crossing cultural boundaries and involving end users is playing a part in research approaches such as Rapid Rural Appraisal (RRA) and Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) (Chambers, 1997). Since the 1970s, RRA and PRA have been developed to understand and involve (poor, rural) people living in a context that differs much from the *outsider’s* (Western aid workers) cultural background. The techniques have been applied in a variety of sectors but not in design.

In the study for this paper we approach RRA, PRA and CMTs as three sets of techniques, all basically developed to understand people and their context to support the design of improvements to their quality of life. These sets of techniques have in common that they help *the outsider* to gain insights in the needs and desires of the local people, using a variety of (often visually supported) techniques, typically with a high involvement of the local group. However, the techniques have been developed in different disciplines, with different starting points and described in different frames. We compare in order

to learn what CMTs can learn from RRA and PRA. In the following sections the different sets of techniques are described. Then, the relation between the techniques is explained and conclusions are drawn on how they are similar and different and directions for improvement are identified.

This study, limits to a comparison only. Another paper (van Boeijen and Stappers, 2011) presents a more detailed study for the application of contextmapping techniques in non-Western situations, leading to practical guidelines and new techniques.

RURAL APPRAISAL TECHNIQUES

In describing the techniques, we base ourselves largely on descriptions of the methods by Chambers (1994, 1997, 2007). PRA and RRA techniques have been developed for the development and implementation of Natural Resource Management, Agriculture, Health & Nutrition and Urban Planning. RRA was developed in the late 1970s and 1980s. It attempts to help ‘outsiders’ (researchers from universities, institutes, NGOs) to understand *insiders* (poor people living in rural areas). Traditional extractive questionnaire surveys had been found unsatisfactory to gain this understanding; they were time-consuming, biases were hard to overcome, results were poor and the long reports were difficult to use. RRA represents an approach that consists of a variety of techniques that extracted qualitative data to counter these drawbacks (hence the name ‘Rapid’). It gained more and more respect that this qualitative methods did not produce the validity of the quantitative techniques, despite criticism from traditional scientists.

PRA arose in the 1990s and focused on a greater role for the *insiders* (hence the name 'Participatory'). A growing awareness had arisen that the 'insiders' have the capabilities to analyse their situation best by themselves. This led to a research approach where the *insiders* were seen as participants that could be empowered to solve problems by themselves. Therefore, the role of the *outsider* moved from a *researcher* to a *facilitator*, the used methods/techniques from *closed* to *open*, from *verbal* to *visual* and from *measuring* to *comparing*. The relationship between *outsiders* and *insiders* moved from *top down* to *partnership and sharing* and from the *individual* to *group* and the attitude and behaviour from *formal* to *informal and fun*. In table 1 the columns (except rightmost) show a clear move from an *outsider* (researcher) centred approach to a fully *insider* (poor people in rural area's) centered one. The activities of the *outsider* changed from *understanding* (researcher) via *empowering* (coach) to *empowering and teaching* (coach and teacher). Simultaneously, the role of the *insiders* could move from a passive one to an active role, steering one's own development process. RRA methods are more verbal and PRA methods more visual.

Further variants of the techniques emerged. Participatory Learning and Action (PLA) was added in 1995 to emphasize even more the need to unite understanding, effectuation and evaluation with the *insiders* (Chambers 2007). In the International HIV/AIDS Alliance (2006) PLA has been explained as:

A growing family of approaches, tools, attitudes and behaviours to enable and empower people to present, share, analyse and enhance their knowledge of life and conditions, and to plan, act, monitor, evaluate, reflect and scale up community action and a way to help people to participate together in learning, and then to act on that learning.

Similarly, the Visualization in Participatory Programs (VIPP) (Unicef, 1993) comprises a package of techniques to empower poor people by providing a combination of different visualized tools with the aim of enabling insider's participation in solving development problems. The last two are cited to

illustrate the variety of names representing sets of techniques used in development programmes. The comparison is limited to RRA and PRA, since they cover the basic principles and techniques.

CMTS FOR DESIGN

Similar developments have happened in Industrial Product Design in Europe and the USA over the past two decades. Concerns for end users needs, techniques to study them and to involve end users in evaluating, informing and conceiving new products rose steadily over this period. Design approaches such as participatory design and co-design involve end users in various roles in the product design process. In the rapidly growing field of 'design ethnography' and user-centred design, various ways of involving end users emerged (Sanders and Stappers, 2008). Contextmapping is one of the outcomes.

As the name suggests, contextmapping techniques were developed to let designers and researchers create a map of the context of the user and product use. CMTs are generative research techniques to gain richer understanding from people about their everyday life. They help people to observe parts of their own environment and life, to reflect on this and to express their tacit and latent knowledge (insights that people do not come up with immediately). These insights, in their turn, provide inspiration and information that can direct the conceptual phase of design and product development.

Contextmapping (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005) combines several research methods (interviews, observations, generative techniques and elements from cultural probes) in order to generate rich experience information. Starting points are: (1) the intended users are approached as the experts of their experiences, (2) facilitators use designerly tools to elicit experiences, (3) the aim is to look for functional as well as emotional aspects and (4) the aim is to provide insights which are actionable for designers.

The *standard* sequence student designers learn is described in detail in Sleeswijk Visser et al. (2005). It is divided into six stages: (1) preparation, (2) sensitization, (3) sessions (make & say and discussion), (4) analysis, (5) communication (capture

	RRA	PRA	CMTs
1. Period of major development	Late 1970s, 1980s	Late 1980s, 1990s	Late 1990s, 2000s
2. Major innovators based in	Universities	NGOs	Universities
3. Main users at first	Aid agencies, universities	NGOs, government field organizations	Designers, universities, companies
4. Key resource earlier undervalued	Local people's <i>knowledge</i>	Local people's analytical <i>capabilities</i>	Local people's <i>dreams and needs</i>
5. Main innovations	Methods, team management	Behaviour, experiential learning	Method
6. Predominant mode	Elicitive, Extractive	Facilitating, Participatory	Eliciting and facilitating through co-creation
7. Ideal objectives	Learning by outsiders	Empowerment of local people	Insights for new product ideas
8. Long-term outcomes	Plans, projects, publications	Sustainable local action and institutions	Outsiders

Table 1. RRA and PRA comparison (all columns except rightmost from Chambers, 1994, p.958) compared with CMTs

Nature of process	RRA -----	PRA	CMTs
1. Mode	Extractive -----Elicitive ----- Sharing-----	Empowering	Elicitive ----- Sharing
2. Outsiders' role	Investigator -----	Facilitator	Investigator, facilitator
3. Information owned, analysed and used by	Outsiders -----	Local people	Outsiders
4. Methods used	Mainly RRA plus sometimes PRA -----	Mainly PRA plus sometimes RRA	CMTs

Table 1. The RRA -PRA continuum (all columns except rightmost from Chambers, 1994, p. 959) compared with CMTs.

and share) and (6) conceptualization. During the preparation, the focus for the study is set and tools, such as diaries and collage-making kits, are designed. In the sensitization stage, participants receive a package with e.g. a photo-camera and a workbook, to record and reflect on some of their daily routines, or on certain parts of their lives. This *homework* should make the participants sensitive to the topic they will encounter in the third stage, the (group) sessions. In these sessions participants make expressive artefacts, such as collages, story- and timelines, 3D models and maps. In the fourth stage these physical expressions and (transcripts of) the discussions of participants' thoughts and dreams are analysed by the researcher(s), either with or without involvement of participating users or the designers. In the fifth stage results are prepared for communication to other stakeholders, such as a design team in a company. Finally the conceptualization stage can start. In practice, there are many variants of this standard sequence.

Ingredients and course of events may also differ, depending on the aim and context of the project.

RESEARCH APPROACH: WHAT DID WE WANT TO KNOW AND HOW?

The central question in this study is: What can designers learn from Rapid Rural Appraisal and Participatory Rural Appraisal for the use of contextmapping techniques in a BoP project?

To answer this question several research methods were applied. Firstly, the study is based on the *first author's experience* with designing for BoP and lessons from student projects such as Kikoa. Furthermore, insights from former projects are used as *cases*. From 2008 till 2010, several dozens of academic and industrial design projects with professional partners have been intensively monitored and evaluated. In those projects a variety of such contextual research techniques as mentioned earlier were applied.

A further source was a set of thirty-four essays, in which master students, industrial design, reflected on the theory, using both their own experiences in projects (*cases*) and *literature*. All students had been taught the contextmapping framework. Thirteen were international students from outside Europe, which means that they had already experienced substantial cultural shifts when coming to Delft. Twenty students discussed difficulties and opportunities of applying CMT in cultures they were not familiar with, using literature and own experiences in applying CMTs in design projects abroad. The other fourteen students reflected on discussions in the academic literature. They made a comparison between three sets of techniques: RRA, PRA and CMTs. After this review we conducted an additional literature research about RRA and PRA. (cases and literature)

These qualitative data, with differences and similarities between the different approaches, have been collected and clustered in a large matrix and refined in an iterative process. Those aspects that rose to the surface have been translated into five guidelines for users of contextmapping techniques.

RESULTS: WHAT DID WE FIND?

The comparison clearly shows that all three sets of methods, PRA, RRA and CMTs, were developed for *outsiders* to contribute effectively and efficiently to the quality of people's lives. All types make use of group sessions and generative techniques using visual information, paying attention to a relaxed situation with room for playful expression in order to gain a rich understanding of people's life. Table 1, based on the RRA - PRA comparison (Chambers, 1994) summarizes main commonalities and differences. Table 2 gives additional aspects that were not discussed by Chambers.

Although CMTs are the youngest in the family, the overview does not show a move into one direction. Most outstanding difference is that PRA emphasizes the importance of the *empowerment* of local people, supporting them to use their own capabilities, while CMTs are mainly used to *inform* the design team. In PRA much attention is paid to biases of both outsiders and insiders, manifested, for instance, in the selection on location (nearby big cities), participants (elites more than poor), season (dry and

cool rather than hot and wet) and attitude (diplomatic rather than causing offence) (Chambers, 1994, p.956). It is stressed that outsiders do not dominate and lecture, but have an open mind, attitude and behaviour, facilitating local people. This importance is illustrated with two quotes:

'Dominant behaviour by outsiders may explain why it has taken until the 1990s for the analytical capabilities of local people to better be recognized and for PRA to emerge, grow and spread.' (Chambers, 1994, pp.953-996).

'People with little education were much more capable of doing their own appraisal and analysis than professionals believed.' (Chambers 2007, p.9)

Students do learn that before starting contextmapping sessions they need to make their presumptions about their participants explicit by drawing mind maps and discussing the outcomes with each other and reflecting on them in a later stage. However, the influences of participants' biases are not discussed. In contextmapping sessions both eliciting and facilitating occur, but the facilitation aims to support the personal expression of the participants, not to empower them to solve their own problems and to facilitate their learning process. Even though, through co-creation participants partly have a steering role in the development process, the outsiders make key decisions. This is essentially different from PRA, in which the ideal situation participants are supposed to take the lead and outsiders do not collect data, but in which the data are shared, owned and analysed by the local people themselves.

Table 2 lists distinguishing aspects that do not appear in the previous tables. With CMTs the outsider tries to tap into the knowledge source of participants that they are not consciously aware of and that is hard to communicate, such as the culture they are living in. These mainly generative techniques evoke this *latent* knowledge of the participants, more than the analytic techniques used in PRA. Besides, these generative explorations are often starting more 'off topic', away from the problem, providing a space for new and unexpected

	RRA	PRA	CMT
1. Context	People living in poor, rural areas	People living in poor, rural areas	People living in Western situations
2. Knowledge source	Explicit, observable (what people say and do)	Observable, tacit (what people say, do and think)	Tacit, latent (what people say, do and think, dream unconsciously)
3. Used techniques	Semi-structured interviews Transect walks with observations Mapping and diagramming	Group sessions with room for fun and expression, using a variety of tools: visual and tangible such as: Diagramming Mapping Drama Observing Scoring, linking, ranking, comparing	Group sessions with room for fun and expression, using a variety of tools: visual and tangible such as: Generative techniques e.g.: Cultural probes Info graphics Persona's Scenario's Self observation & reflection
4. Research location	People in own living environment	People in own living environment Participation in small groups	People in an organized setting Participation in groups
5. Research materials		Local materials such as: sand, stones, seeds; not permanent and portable: documentation needed Visuals to overcome language problems	Post-its, paper, pencils, markers, camera's, stickers Well prepared and structured Visuals for empathizing, expression and understanding
6. Time needed	Faster than quantitative data through questionnaires	Time-consuming, adjusted to time perception local people	Time-consuming
7. Domains of application	Natural resource management Agriculture Programmes for equity, empowerment, rights and security Community-level planning and action		Product design and product service systems

Table 2. Comparison of RRA, PRA and CMT: additional aspects.

insights. The tools are often designed for or adjusted to the specific situation. In the sensitizing booklets used in the Kikoa project, for instance, our design students inserted elements that Kenyan participants were familiar with such as the Kiswahili proverbs on kangas (colourful garments worn by women) translated to a personal favourite slogan on a T-shirt. Another difference is the location where sessions take place and the used materials such as sand, stones and seeds and visuals to overcome language problems. To bridge the cultural gap between the outsiders and the insiders, PRA occurs in a local environment and with local materials. Contextmapping sessions often take place in a

company or consultancy building, using state-of-the-art materials such as flip-over, post-its, markers, videos, photos and cameras, sometimes combined with Internet applications.

Furthermore, much more attention is paid to capture results from the sessions, for instance, by making personas and info graphics. This extra attention for communication is needed, because often results have to be handed over to other stakeholders within the product design process.

Finally, the time needed for a session differs slightly. RRA was developed, because it was faster than questionnaires. However, PRA and contextmapping sessions are time-consuming. Designers using CMTs

are used to urbanized situations in which people are exposed to fast moving interactions and changes. In rural areas people are used to interact more slowly, partly due to a lack of fast means for communication (e.g. computers, Internet and transport vehicles). Thus, preparation and execution of contextmapping sessions will take extra time in poor rural areas. Some students made the wrong assumption that people living in poor areas have more free time than people in living in Western areas and thus will have time to join their sessions. The opposite is often true; time is important since poor people need to work extra, need to be flexible, reacting to every opportunity to earn money. They cannot use the means that make life fast and comfortable. In a reflection on the development of PRA since 1990, Chambers writes:

'Much training neglected or totally ignored behaviour and attitudes. PRA was routinized, people's time was taken and their expectations raised without any outcome, methods were used to extract information not to empower...' (Chambers, 2007, p. 286).

In a contextmapping session of the Kikoa project, participants were wondering why they should share all their experiences for this project. They could not understand how these experiences would contribute to the aim of the project to design a mobile academy.

CONCLUSIONS: WHAT DID WE LEARN FROM RURAL APPRAISAL TECHNIQUES FOR CONTEXTMAPPING IN BOP PROJECTS?

In the previous section the results of a comparison between RRA and PRA and CMTs is presented. The study reveals a variety of differences and similarities between the three research approaches.

These outcomes have been clustered and translated into five guidelines for designers who want to use contextmapping techniques in poor rural areas where people live with a cultural background that differs much from their own.

1. Empowerment of local people.

If outsiders, in our case product designers, want to contribute to the improvement of people's lives, as they do in BoP projects, they need to pay extra attention to the capabilities of the local people. Then, the elicitation of needs and dreams of the local people should not only serve the design task of the designer, but also empower the local people to design for themselves. Incorporating design education and providing time and space for the collection of data and analyses by the local people themselves should then be included. Outcomes from sessions should be captured and handed over to the participants.

2. Using local materials and locations.

In order to bridge the cultural gap it is recommended to use materials that people are familiar with and that they can still use after the project. This will support the empowerment of people, making them feel less dependent on the outsiders' input. Local and cheap materials also stimulate to act and use them; a high quality expensive post-it can be perceived as something one would not like to spoil with a low quality sketch.

3. Scheduling time.

PRA emphasizes the need to adjust to the local people's perception of pace of time, which is much slower than outsiders are used to. For the duration of contextmapping sessions, more time, probably twice as much, should be planned. The time spent should be valuable for participants.

4. Overcoming bias from both the outsider and local people.

RRA and PRA heavily stress the influence of biases of the outsiders as well as the local people. Careful selection of the facilitators of contextmapping sessions, on age, gender, education and cultural background can help to limit biases of the local people. In contextmapping a short session to overcome biases is included, but because of the large differences between outsiders and insiders, biases can be very strong and may need extra attention.

5. Attitude of outsider; managing PRE.

RRA and PRA heavily stress the importance of the attitude and behaviour of the facilitator, who should be open-minded and act bottom-up instead of top-down. As an outsider, it is essential to gain respect and trust of the insiders. We summarize this in the management of PRE: Permission (P) from, for instance local authorities such as a village chief is often needed. Reciprocity (R) between participants and facilitators protects the balance between give and take, which motivates people. A gift or loan might be appropriate. Expectations (E) about the contribution of facilitators and participants between both parties should be clear in advance to gain trust and credibility.

Figure 2. Outsiders need to manage Permission, Reciprocity and Expectations to cross cultural chasms (van Boeijen and Stappers, 2011)

DISCUSSION

This paper presents similarities and differences between rural appraisal and contextmapping techniques.

Since there is an overlap between the different approaches the question rises if these clear distinguishing labels are needed. The authors agree with Chambers' (1994, p.958) answer.

'Labelling supports the pride of ownership and that it is strengthening commitment, enthusiasm and good work among its practitioners. Moreover, it can help to clearly indicate what belongs where and thus providing the possibility to criticise a specific method when applied not as intended.'

This labelling makes designers responsible for their applied tools and techniques. The question if designers should follow the guidelines can be answered from an ethical as well as a pragmatic perspective.

The development and application of RRA and PRA seem to be highly driven by ethical values and the belief that fortunate, privileged people should support those who are underprivileged escape from poverty and that a democratic, bottom-up approach should be the right way to achieve this. The Honey Bee Network, 'a voice of creative grassroots innovators and traditional knowledge holders' (Gupta, 2010), and the initiating Fab Labs, initiated by MIT, show this move from a top-down to a bottom-up approach to support underserved people. Also among designers there is an increasing interest in improving people's lives by giving them a larger role in the design process for ethical reasons. This is, for instance, manifested in a growing acceptance of BoP projects in our university and in the wide-spread acceptance of design approaches within the design community, such as inclusive design and co-creation and social responsible design contests such as the Index Award: Design to Improve Life. Nevertheless, for a designer the joy to master one's own, personal creation process may conflict with the ethical stance that people should be empowered to design by himself or herself.

From a pragmatic point of view there are also reasons to move to a bottom-up approach. For instance, involving intended users in the creation process builds up a basis for acceptance of innovation. This is relevant for design projects in which commitment of local people is important, for instance, when local production is part of the solution or when the product cannot easily be sold by a single message. Furthermore, it increases the acceptability of products, assuming that bottom-up involvement will lead to better understanding of intended users and their local context and subsequently lead to better ideas, which are appropriate for their intended users. Intensively involvement of local intended users is also important to avoid mistakes caused by a designer's *blind spots* for the deeper motivations, interests, routines, needs and dreams of the unknown users, both as individuals and as members of groups. Understanding the local cultural and physical context is essential; appropriate product designs cannot be based on universal principles of human behaviour and physics

only. For outsiders it is impossible to fully understand a culture within a few months, as spent in a student's BoP project. Therefore, the involvement of the 'experts of their experience' (insiders) is needed to avoid unnecessary mistakes. Another pragmatic reason to involve and also empower people to design by their own is that the investment in people's potential enlarges the possibilities for new product designs. In 'Beyond Couch Potatoes' Fischer (2002) explains which possibilities for CHI designs are arising if people can be seen not only as consumers, but also as designers. For that reasons a bottom-up approach, integrated in contextmapping activities in BoP projects, empowering and educating intended users may create a breeding ground for new products designed by professional designers that support consumers to become designers.

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